

Psychopathy, Ex-Offender Reintegration, and Social Supports: Bringing it All Together

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Abstract

Long-standing disagreement among clinicians and scientists about the conceptual underpinnings of psychopathy has resulted in the term being used interchangeably with antisocial personality to describe people with limited affective reactions as dangerous, unresponsive to therapeutic interventions, and especially common in prison populations. Increasingly, research is beginning to reveal the inaccuracy of these assumptions, and to question some of the practices that have become commonplace in relation to them. This paper reviews some of these issues and proposes a case study to examine their impact on post-incarceration adjustment and reintegration.

Introduction

The academic and scientific confusion surrounding constructs like psychopathy and anti-social personality materially impact the ex-offender's ability to reintegrate with the community.

Methods

The materials in this review, which span the years from 1974 through 2014, were derived primarily through the use of search terms in the Psycinfo Base and Google Scholar, including "psychopath," "anti-social personality," "psychopathy in prisons," "psychopathy among the incarcerated," and so on. Seminal materials were identified in the reference sections of previous research. Primary texts, like the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, fifth edition (2013), and the *International Classification of Diseases*, tenth edition (2010), were used to identify current clinical applications. In general, the purpose of the review was to identify the history of the constructs examined in this paper as they relate to research, jurisprudence, community attitudes, and ex-offender reintegration.

Review

There are two widely held ideas about psychopathy that are both inaccurate and problematic. The first is that psychopathy is common among the incarcerated (Fazel & Danesh, 2002; Coid, Yang, Ullrich, Roberts, Moran, Bebbington, and Hare, 2009). The second is that psychopaths are extraordinarily cunning and dangerous people beyond the reach of most clinical interventions (Coid et al., 2009; cf. Skeem, Polaschek, Patrick, and Lilienfeld, 2011). Given that much criminal behavior seems to involve a callous disregard for the rights of crime victims, it is almost too easy to understand how the lay public comes to regard prisoners as remorseless and predatory. What is not so easy to understand is that psychopathy is not a diagnostic classification

in the DSM-5 or the ICD-10, that researchers are still not in agreement about what the term actually means from a clinical point of view (Skeem et al., 2011; Wilks-Riley & Ireland, 2012; Smith, Edens, Clark, and Rulseh, 2014), and that the nature of some research seems likely to contribute to the furtherance of the lay public's misconceptions. These issues have advocacy implications, particularly as advocacy relates to efforts to help former inmates to reintegrate into community life (Prins, 2014).

The idea that prisons are full of psychopaths derives from several sources, some professional and some not. The most important source of the confusion, however, derives from the overlap in the professional descriptions of the “psychopathic personality” and the “antisocial personality,” which intersect at various points, most particularly as the descriptions relate to affect. A psychopathic personality is someone with an “affective deficiency” (Coid et al, 2009), an “emotional detachment” (Wilks-Riley & Ireland, 2012), someone with “no more than fleeting, surface emotions” (Skeem et al., 2011). Comparatively, the British Psychological Society and the Royal College of Psychiatrists (NCCMH, 2013) describes people with antisocial personality as those with “low conscientiousness” (NCCMH, 2013), and the American Psychiatric Association, in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM-5), describes them as being “callous” (764).

Stated alternatively, “[v]arious terms have been used to describe those who consistently exploit others and infringe rules for personal gain as a consequence of personality traits, including antisocial personality disorder, sociopathy, and psychopathy” (NCCMH, 2013, 14). The overlap, in other words, has resulted in the terms being used synonymously in professional circles and elsewhere (cf. Skeem, et al., 2011; Edens & Cox, 2012). It is an old problem:

In a 1952 revision of the psychiatric nomenclature the term psychopathic personality was officially replaced by sociopathic personality. Subsequently the informal term, sociopath, was often used along with the older and more familiar psychopath to designate a large group of seriously disabled people, listed with other dissimilar groups under the heading personality disorder. Still another change in the official terminology was made in 1968 when the designation sociopathic personality was replaced by personality disorder, antisocial type. In referring to these people now formally classified by the term antisocial personality, I shall continue to use also the more familiar and apparently more durable term, psychopath. (Cleckley, 1988, pp. 11)

This long-standing tendency to use the terms interchangeably has had enormous consequences for the discourse on mental health because prevalence studies consistently report that “people with mental illnesses are overrepresented in the criminal justice system” (Prins, 2014; Rotter, Way, Steinbacher, Sawyer, and Smith, 2002), and the overrepresentation is mostly, so we are told, men with antisocial personality disorder (Fazel & Danesh, 2002).

Estimates on the prevalence of antisocial personality among the incarcerated vary depending on the source (DSM-5; Rotter et al, 2002), but most agree with Robert Trestman’s (2000) assessment that the condition is “endemic to correctional settings” (p. 233) in the United States and elsewhere (Fazel and Danesh, 2002). Indeed, the estimates are so high that the subtitle of a paper on personality disorders in correctional settings by Rotter et al. (2002) would ask “aren’t they all antisocial?” In fact, as the paper goes on to demonstrate, the answer is no. Although personality disorders are common among prisoners, and antisocial personality is the

most common subtype, the overall prevalence of antisocial personality is nothing like 100%. “They are not all antisocial” (Rotter et al., 2002, p.346).

Disagreements about prevalence are but the tip of the iceberg. As noted earlier, debate continues about what psychopathy is and what it is not (Skeem et al., 2011), with researchers generally falling into one of two groups: those who believe psychopathy is categorically distinct (cf. Edens, Marcus, Lilienfeld, and Poythress, 2006) and those who believe psychopathy is a dimension of antisocial personality (Coid & Ullrich, 2010; Skeem et al., 2011). The problem, as Lilienfeld (1994) observed some time ago, “stem[s] largely from a fundamental disagreement regarding the conceptualization of the syndrome itself” (p. 18; c.f. Skeem & Cooke, 2010). Blackburn’s (1988) more pointed remarks go so far as to assert that the concepts are “mythical” and useless (p. 511).

Of course, a reasonable question at this point is why any of this should matter. The answer is that the interchangeability of terms and lack of conceptual agreement among clinicians and scientists impacts the manner in which these terms are understood and applied in the community. The idea that antisocial personality/psychopathy is common among the incarcerated (Trestman, 2000; Fazel & Danesh, 2002) or that these people are all dangerous and incurable (NCCMH, 2013; Skeem et al., 2011; Edens & Cox, 2012), for instance, becomes the backdrop for conversations among politicians and lawyers and writers and criminal justice advocates and movie goers and so on. Some of these conversations are probably entertaining. As Skeem et al. (2011) observed, “[f]ew psychological concepts evoke...as much fascination and misunderstanding” (p. 96).

Other conversations, however, would not be considered entertaining as they revolve around incredibly weighty questions at sentencing in criminal cases, like whether a person’s

actions evince some kind of permanent and irrevocable mental dysfunction that necessitates lifetime incarceration or even the death penalty. Although the United States Supreme Court recently struck down the rights of states to employ the death penalty in the adjudication of adolescents in *Roper v. Simmons* (2005), this is only a recent development. The conversation in the courtroom prior to this decision was that adolescents as young as sixteen and seventeen (*Stanford v. Kennedy*, 1989) could be put to death. Justice Kennedy's reliance on our "evolving standards of decency" notwithstanding, the change in the Court's position does not reflect a change in its understanding of psychopathy/antisocial personality or even agreement among the Justices about the appropriate penalty for children in capital cases. That is, changes in the law do not necessarily equal changes in the way people think about something. As demonstrated recently in the work of Smith et al. (2014), the most common associations for the word psychopath are "infamous serial killers and mass murderers (e.g., Ted Bundy, Charles Manson, and Jeffrey Dahmer)" (p. 494). Even when presented with expert information to the contrary, ideas about psychopathy are not "swayed appreciably" (Smith et al., 2014, p. 497). Application of the term does appreciably influence the juror's willingness to levy the harshest possible penalties, however (Smith et al.; Edens & Cox, 2012).

In recent years, much of the discourse relating to psychopathy/antisocial personality has been driven by the use of Robert Hare's Psychopathy Checklist-Revised (PCL-R). The number of studies either making use of the PCL-R or examining the instrument itself in some way is astonishing. While some writers have described this apparent dominance as "generative" (Skeem et al., 2011), they have also described it as "conflating measures with constructs" (Skeem & Cooke, 2010; Cooke et al., 2007; Lilienfeld, 1994)—that is, confusing scores on the PCL-R with psychopathy itself. Reifying psychopathy and turning it into something sentencing courts and

parole boards can use to assess the potential for violence or the likelihood of recidivist behavior, though desirable, is an extraordinarily problematic development at the present time. Murrie, Boccaccini, Johnson, and Janke (2007), for example, have recently found that differences in raters' assessments using the PCL-R are attributable to rater's effort to satisfy whoever is paying for the assessment (p. 352). An underlying assumption of the PCL-R is that those with psychopathy are categorically different from everyone else. Thus, the discourse among those who utilize the instrument is that those who score high on the PCL-R are categorically psychopathic. Although it is undoubtedly true that judges and prosecutors appreciate the definitiveness and the certainty the PCL-R promises, they are not competent to assess the instrument's construct validity or discern variations among raters' applications of the device. While the discourse surrounding outcomes for people who commit crimes is surely not a priority for most people, "the fact that most of the roughly 2.3 million incarcerated individuals will be released" (Prins, 2014, p. 867) demands more attention, both in how we think about those incarcerated and how we think about ourselves: "Although violent criminals high in psychopathy may not...engender...much sympathy, it is questionable whether psychologists should contribute to the popular prejudice that these individuals are qualitatively different from other humans" (Marcus, John, and Edens, 2004, p. 633).

"Pathological disease is not cured" declared Donald Trump in a stump speech aired on *CBS This Morning* (Licht, 2015). Another reckless verbal harpoon hurled across the political landscape as the republican front runner for the highest office in the United States set his sights on Ben Carson. Ben Carson is a black man and, by his own admission, once a conduct disordered youth inclined to extreme violence. The details are 50 years in the past, lost to everyone apparently but Ben Carson, who went on to become a world class neurosurgeon and a serious

contender for the Presidency. The message in Ben Carson's story, delivered in a country where one of every three black men is expected to end up incarcerated (Kerby, 2012; Knafo, 2013; Mauer & King, 2007), is that your story can be different if you want it to, that you can still do great things even if you get off to a bad start. Trump's message, in contrast, is that you should not be allowed to go on to do great things, that no one should trust you ever again. Trump, of course, is attempting to tap into the public's fear. He wants the public to look at Carson and be reminded of what it knows about 33% of the nation's black minority, that it is incarcerated or will be, and that incarcerated people have mental health problems you cannot fix.

Like other issues in the discussion of psychopathic/antisocial personalities, the public perception of psychopathy as strictly negative owes much to the technical and academic environments in which these concepts are developed. In fact, much of the criticism regarding the conceptual underpinnings of these terms, aside from the "wavering outlines" decried by Lewis in 1974 (p. 133), is precisely their focus on maladaptive behaviors (Wilks-Riley & Ireland, 2012; Skeem & Cooke, 2010; Rotter et al., 2002). Wilks-Riley and Ireland (2012), for instance, found that "psychopathic traits are not routinely predicted by negative characteristics, as some have suggested..., and that schemas associated with personality difficulties are not purely maladaptive..." (p. 481). Similarly, Skeem and Cooke (2010) have taken exception with the view "that crime is central to psychopathy" (p. 455), expressing the view that this idea has "become a barrier to scientific progress" (p. 455). Perhaps most telling of all in this context is the quiet admonition of Marcus et al. (2004) who remind us that there is an ethical component to this discussion. While it may be the case that changes in our professional

and scientific position will not have an immediate impact on law, it can have an immediate impact on our discipline if we just choose our words more carefully (p. 633).

The concerns expressed by Marcus et al. (2004) say a good deal about the practical consequences of doing research, on the one hand, and being a researcher, on the other. Specifically, the idea that research does not always result in an immediate improvement in the real world, that practical consequences as a result of research are sometimes slow to arrive if they arrive at all. The researcher does not get to choose how the world will respond to the information he or she is providing. What the researcher does get to choose is how he or she will respond. In the present instance, the researcher chose to advocate by reminding us that sometimes little things like word choice can go a long way.

Assuredly, people labeled psychopathic or antisocial and serving prison sentences have often done egregious things to get themselves identified as such, and the public's inclination to think of characters like Hannibal Lecter when they hear the word psychopath is not without some precedent. Acknowledging this, however, does not change the fact that the vast majority of the incarcerated will be released into the community (Prins, 2014), that they will need the community's support in order to reintegrate successfully, or that most of them are nothing like Hannibal Lecter even if they do have numerous mental health problems.

The barriers facing prisoners returning to community life are substantial, and include everything from limitations in their physical health to a complete lack of the material resources (Prins, 2014). Former prisoners are "denied public housing, employment in numerous fields, income support, education subsidies, supplemental nutrition assistance, and participation in civic institutions such as jury duty and political franchise" (Prins, 2014, p. 869). It seems to this writer that the difficulties facing formerly incarcerated persons are likely to increase by no small

margin if they find themselves in community settings that choose to revile them, vilify them, ostracize them, and so on. Citing Ernest Drucker, Prins (2014) reports that 4.8 million people are on parole or probation, and 43% of them will be rearrested within 3 years of their release. It behooves us to see beyond the stereotypes.

Summary and Conclusions

Mental health problems are common among the incarcerated and range across most of the classificatory divisions of the DSM-5 (Prins, 2015; Diamond, Wang, Holzer, Thomas, and Crusier, 2001). The widespread incidence of mental health issues, however, does not reflect a preponderance of antisocial or psychopathic personalities who are dangerous and incurable. Although the incidence of mental health problems is greater in prisons, and the environment presents special problems clinicians need to be aware of (Rotter et al., 2002), people in prison are treatable. While much of the research in recent decades has gone a long way in establishing the primacy of the PCL-R to psychopathy, more recent developments have brought some of these results into question, particularly the idea that psychopathy is a distinct category, that the people so identified are especially different from everyone else, or even that criminality is central to the underlying construct. These issues have tangible consequences for approximately 4.8 million people in the United States alone.

References

- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). Washington, DC: Author.
- Blackburn, R. (1988). On moral judgements and personality disorders. The myth of psychopathic personality revisited. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 153, 505-512. . doi:10.1192/bjp.153.4.505
- Chu, W., Dialla, P., Roignot, P., Lepinoy, M., Poillot, M., Coutant, C., Arveux, P... (2016). Determinants of quality of life among long-term breast cancer survivors. *Quality of Life Research*, 25, 1982-1990. doi: 10.1007/s11136-016-1248-z
- Cleckley, H. (1976). *The mask of sanity* (5th ed.). St. Louis, MO: Mosby.
- Coid, J., & Ullrich, S. (2010). Antisocial personality disorder is on a continuum with psychopathy. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 51(4), 426-433.
- Coid, J., Yang, M., Ullrich, S., Roberts, A., Moran, P., Bebbington, P., Hare, R. (2009). Psychopathy among prisoners in England and Wales. *International Journal of Law and psychiatry*, 32, 134-141. doi:10.1016/j.ijlp.2009.02.008
- Cooke, D., Michie, C., & Skeem, J. (2007). Understanding the structure of the Psychopathy Checklist - Revised: An exploration of methodological confusion. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 190(Suppl. 49), 39-50. doi:10.1192/bjp.190.5.s39
- Diamond, M., Wang, E, Holzer, C, Thomas, C., & Crusser, A. The prevalence of mental illness in prison. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health*, 29(1), 21-40.
- Edens, J., Marcus, D., Lilienfeld, S., & Poythress, N. (2006). Psychopathic, Not Psychopath:

- Taxometric Evidence for the Dimensional Structure of Psychopathy. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 115(1), 131-144. doi:10.1037/0021-843X.115.1.131
- Edens, J., & Cox, J. (2012). Examining the Prevalence, Role and Impact of Evidence Regarding Antisocial Personality, Sociopathy and Psychopathy in Capital Cases: A Survey of Defense Team Members. *Behavioral Sciences & the Law*, 30(3), 239- 255. doi:10.1002/bsl.2009
- Fazel, S., & Danesh, J. (2002). Serious mental disorder in 23 000 prisoners: A systematic review of 62 surveys. *The Lancet*, 359, 545-550. Retrieved November 13, 2015, from thelancet.com.
- Kerby, S. (2012). The top ten most startling facts about people of color and criminal justice in the United States. Center for American Progress. Retrieved from americanprogress.org
- Knafo, S. (2013). 1 in 3 blacks will go to prison in their lifetime, report warns. *Huffington Post*. Retrieved from huffingtonpost.com
- Lewis, A. (1974). Psychopathic personality: A most elusive category. *Psychological Medicine*, 4, 133-140.
- Licht, C. (Producer). (2015, November 8). *CBS this morning* [television broadcast]. New York, NY: Central Broadcasting Service.
- Lilienfeld, S. (1994). Conceptual problems in the assessment of psychopathy. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 14(1), 17-38.
- Marcus, D., John, S., & Edens, J. (2004). Taxometric Analysis of Psychopathic Personality.

Journal of Abnormal Psychology, 113(4), 626-635. doi:10.1037/0021-843X.113.4.626

Mauer, M. and King, R. (2007). *Uneven justice: State rates of incarceration by race and ethnicity*. The Sentencing Project. Washington, DC

Murrie, D., Boccaccini, M., Johnson, J., & Janke, C. (2007). Does interrater (dis)agreement on Psychopathy Checklist scores in sexually violent predator trials suggest partisan allegiance in forensic evaluations? *Law and Human Behavior*, 352-362. doi:10.1007/s10979-007-9097-5

National Collaborating Centre for Mental Health (2013). *Antisocial personality disorder: the NICE guideline on treatment, management and prevention*. National clinical practice guideline number 77. The British Psychological Society and the Royal College of Psychiatrists.

Prins, S. (2014). Prevalence of Mental Illnesses in U.S. State Prisons: A Systematic Review. *Psychiatric Services*, 65(7), 862-872. doi:10.1176/appi.ps.201300166

Roper v. Simmons, 543 U.S. 551 (2005).

Rotter, M., Way, B., Steinbacher, M., Sawyer, D., & Smith, H. (2002). Personality disorders in prison: Aren't they all antisocial? *Psychiatric Quarterly*, 73(4), 337-349.

Sander, A., Fuchs, K., High, W., Hall, K., Kreutzer, J., & Rosenthal, M. (1999). The community integration questionnaire revisited: an assessment of factor structure and validity. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 80, 1303-1308.

Sarason, I., Levine, R. Basham, R., & Sarason, B. (1983). Assessing social support. *Journal*

- of Personality and Social Psychology*, 44, 127-139.
- Skeem, J., & Cooke, D. (2010). One measure does not a construct make: Directions toward reinvigorating psychopathy research—reply to Hare and Neumann (2010). *Psychological Assessment*, 22(2), 455-459.
- Skeem, J., Polaschek, D., Patrick, C., & Lilienfeld, S. (2011). Psychopathic personality: Bridging the gap between scientific evidence and public policy. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 12(3), 95-162. doi:10.1177/1529100611426706
- Smith, S., Edens, J., Clark, J., & Rulseh, A. (2014). “So, what is a psychopath?” Venireperson perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes about psychopathic personality. *Law and Human Behavior*, 38(5), 490-500. doi:10.1037/lhb0000091
- Stanford v. Kennedy, 492 U.S. 361 (1989).
- Trestman, R. (2000). Behind bars: personality disorders. *Journal of the American academy of psychiatry and the law*, 28, 232-235.
- Wilks-Riley, F., & Ireland, J. (2012). Cognition and psychopathy: Identifying negative and positive schemas in general and forensic samples. *Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology*, 23(4), 466-484. doi:10.1080/14789949.2012.694464
- Willer, B., Rosenthal, M., Kreutzer, J., Gordon, W. & Rempel, R. (1993). Assessment of community integration following rehabilitation for traumatic brain injury. *The Journal of Head Trauma Rehabilitation*, 8(2), 75-87. doi.org/10.1097/00001199-199308020-00009
- World Health Organization. (2010). *The international statistical classification of diseases and related health problems* (10th ed.). Malta: Author.